

SCIENTIFIC OUTCOMES OF ARCHAEOLOGICAL INVESTIGATIONS AT
MEDIEVAL RURAL SETTLEMENTS IN CENTRAL SOGD
НАУЧНЫЕ РЕЗУЛЬТАТЫ АРХЕОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ
СРЕДНЕВЕКОВЫХ СЕЛЬСКИХ ПОСЕЛЕНИЙ ЦЕНТРАЛЬНОГО
СОГДА
MARKAZIY SUG'D O'RTA ASR QISHLOQ MAKONLARIDA OLIV
BORILGAN ARXEOLOGIK TADQIQOTLARNING ILMIY NATIJALARI

Rashidov Sunnatillo Rashid o'g'li

Samarqand davlat universiteti doktoranti

sunnatillorashidov050@gmail.com

Abstract

This article analyzes the main results of archaeological research conducted in the medieval rural areas of Central Sughd during the years of independence. The architectural structures, defense systems, remains of settlements, craft centers, and samples of material culture identified as a result of excavations at the monuments of Kurgan-tepa, Kuldor-tepa, Kafirkala, and Dabusiya are scientifically evaluated. As a result of the research, new information was obtained on the interaction of rural settlements of Central Sughd with cities, their role in socio-economic development, and their significance in the system of the Great Silk Road. The article highlights the importance of archaeological research conducted during the independence period in restoring the medieval history of the region, and summarizes their scientific results.

Keywords: Central Sughd, Middle Ages, rural settlements, archaeological research, Kurgan-tepa, Kuldor-tepa, Kafirkala, Dabusiya, material culture, Great Silk Road.

Аннотация

В статье анализируются основные научные результаты археологических исследований, проведённых на средневековых сельских поселениях Центрального Согда в годы независимости Узбекистана. На основе материалов раскопок городищ Кургонтепа, Кулдортепа, Кафыркала и Дабусия рассматриваются архитектурные сооружения, оборонительные системы, жилые комплексы, ремесленные центры и находки материальной культуры. Исследования позволили получить новые сведения о взаимосвязях сельских поселений с городскими центрами, их роли в социально-экономическом развитии региона и значении в системе Великого шёлкового пути. В статье

обобщаются результаты современных археологических исследований и раскрывается их значение для реконструкции средневековой истории Центрального Согда.

Ключевые слова: Центральный Согд, средневековье, сельские поселения, археологические исследования, Кургонтёпа, Кулдортепа, Кафыркала, Дабусия, материальная культура, Великий шёлковый путь.

Annotatsiya

Mazkur maqolada Markaziy Sugʻdning oʻrta asr qishloq makonlarida mustaqillik yillarida olib borilgan arxeologik tadqiqotlarning asosiy natijalari tahlil qilinadi. Qoʻrgʻontepa, Quldortepa, Kofirqalʼa va Dabusiya yodgorliklarida amalga oshirilgan qazishma ishlari natijasida aniqlangan meʼmoriy inshootlar, mudofaa tizimlari, turar joy qoldiqlari, hunarmandchilik markazlari hamda moddiy madaniyat namunalari ilmiy jihatdan baholanadi. Tadqiqotlar natijasida Markaziy Sugʻd qishloq manzilgohlarining shaharlar bilan oʻzaro aloqalari, ularning ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy rivojlanishdagi oʻrni va Buyuk Ipak yoʻli tizimidagi ahamiyati yuzasidan yangi maʼlumotlar qoʻlga kiritilgan. Maqolada mustaqillik davrida amalga oshirilgan arxeologik izlanishlarning mintaqaning oʻrta asrlar tarixini tiklashdagi ahamiyati yoritilib, ularning ilmiy natijalari umumlashtiriladi.

Kalit soʻzlar: Markaziy Sugʻd, oʻrta asrlar, qishloq manzilgohlari, arxeologik tadqiqotlar, Qoʻrgʻontepa, Quldortepa, Kofirqalʼa, Dabusiya, moddiy madaniyat, Buyuk Ipak yoʻli.

The lack of materials on the material culture of the Zarafshan region in the early Middle Ages in the sources for studying the history of Uzbekistan indicates the need to study this topic as a separate object of study. The sources mention the Middle Zarafshan oasis, which is a region surrounded by mountains on three sides and a steppe only in the west. From a historical and cultural point of view, it is also accepted to call these territories, which unite the Samarkand, Kashkadarya, Bukhara regions of Uzbekistan and the lands around Panjikent in Tajikistan, Samarkand Sughd. It is known from history that the areas from Panjikent to Karmana formed Central Sughd, the capital of which was Samarkand. The districts of the Zarafshan oasis located west of Karmana formed Western Sughd, the capital of which was Bukhara. The districts included in the Kashkadarya oasis formed the lands of Southern Sughd. The upper Kashkadarya districts of Southern Sughd were called the Kesh region, and the lower Kashkadarya districts were called the Nakhshab region. By the High Middle Ages, there were 12 villages and 4 cities in Samarkand Sughd. Six of these villages were located on the

southeast side of the Zarafshan River (Bunjikent, Varaqsar, Ash, Shovdor, Maymug, Sanjarfagn, Abgor, and Rivdad), while the remaining six were located on the north side (Yorkat, Burnamand, Buzmojan, Kabudjakent, Vidar, and Marzban)¹.

The Qorgan-tepa monument is located on the northern side of the Zanjirbagh-ota shrine in the Urgut district. The hill is surrounded by a defensive wall, and on its southern and northern sides is the site of the entrance gate to the arch. Ceramic objects dating back to the 7th-12th centuries have been found around the hill².

The Qorgan-tepa monument may have been a large central city of the Sanjarfagn village. The Sanjarfagn village is located between the Bormish (Abbosaryk, Yangiarik) and Bashmin (Karaunas, Kazanarik) canals, and its center is localized with the Qorgan-tepa archaeological monument located in the village of Eshonravot. The monument consists of an arch, a city hall, and a rabad. In recent years, as a result of soil being removed from the city hall part of the monument by local residents, a number of domed rooms have been found in the section. In 2022, archaeological excavations were carried out on the western side of the arch and on the northwestern side of the arch. As a result of archaeological excavations carried out in the city of Kurgan-Tepa in 2022, settlements dating back to the 7th–8th centuries were discovered and studied. Ash remains recorded on the floors of the rooms allow us to conclude that the settlements were probably destroyed as a result of the Arab attack led by Qutayba ibn Muslim in 712. Pottery vessels from the second construction period date back to the 11th–12th centuries.

Archaeological research in 2023 was carried out in the northern part of the monument arch, measuring 11.75x10 m. Initially, the turf and the underlying soft soil layer were removed from the excavation site. As a result, two construction periods were observed in the excavation site. The location of a mud brick wall (dimensions 50x25x8 cm) belonging to the first construction period was recorded, which ran from east to west in the excavation site, was 10 m long, 1.3 m high, and 2.1–2.2 m wide. The northern side of this wall was plastered with mud mixed with straw³.

The Kuldortepa monument is located 35 km southeast of Samarkand, in the village of Bahrin, Urgut district. The total area of the hill is 17 hectares, surrounded by a 6-meter-high defensive wall. The arch is located on the western side of the city, has a round shape, is surrounded by a moat, and the height of the arch is 15 meters. To the

¹ Бартольд В.В. Туркестан в эпоху монгольского нашествия, Соч. 9 т. М.: Наука, 1963. Ташкент, I. С. 144

² Бердимуратов А.Э., Ронделли Б. Материалы к археологической карте левобережья Зарафшана // ИМКУ, вып. 35.- Самарканд, 2006.-С. 140

³ Сандибоев А.Н., Мураками Т., Бегматов А., Махамадиев Ф. 2023 йилда Кўрғонтепа ёдгорлигида олиб борилган археологик тадқиқотлар, O'zbekistonda arxeologik tadqiqotlar, Samarqand, 2024.389 391 b.

southwest of the arch of the monument, between the Shahrستان and Rabod, there is a separate hill, which the local population calls Kindiktepa, as well as Gishtmasjid. This hill is round in shape, has a diameter of 27 m, and a height of 9.5 m. In 2023, an international joint expedition of Uzbekistan and Japan carried out archaeological excavations in the upper part of the monument. As a result, the location of the prayer house and the adjacent porch, as well as a series of rooms located on the north and west sides, were uncovered and studied⁴.

In the defensive wall located in the northeastern part of the monument, a cut up to 6 m deep was cleared, revealing a 7-row, 44x44x15 cm, mud brick wall with a chamfered surface and a platform underneath. The mud bricks and pottery fragments date back to the 1st century AD. In the early Middle Ages, residences and palaces with central rooms surrounded by a corridor shaped like the letter "G" on two or three sides were widespread. The central room of the Kuldortepa monument is rectangular (4.6x3 m) in shape, surrounded by a corridor shaped like the letter "G". Corridors shaped like the letter "G" are recorded in Afrosiyob, Darband⁵.

As a result of archaeological excavations at the Kuldortepa monument, the objects found in the early medieval layers of the monument include ceramic vessels such as tap vessels, cup-shaped cups, cauldrons, dates, handle-shaped oil jars (mugs), and plates (plates) with the image of pomegranates sprinkled with mica. In addition, coins belonging to the rulers of Sughd from the early medieval period were identified. Written sources indicate that Kuldortepa was the central city of the Maymurg khokimiyat.

The Kafirkala monument is located 18 km south of Samarkand, on the left bank of the Dargam Canal, and its total area is 16 hectares. The monument consists of parts of an ark, a shahrستان, and a rabad, typical of early medieval cities. The arch is square in shape, with sides measuring 76x76 m and a height of 25 m. The arch is surrounded by a moat. According to the city plan, it is closer to a rectangular shape with sides of 360 m. Archaeological excavations in 1990-1994 were carried out in the tower that protruded from the north-west side of the arch. During the excavations, three rooms and a narrow corridor were discovered in the tower. The rooms are located from north to south, their dimensions are 7.85x2.30; 5.40x2; 7.45x2.45 meters. The walls of the rooms are made of alternating layers of raw bricks on a block of bricks, and the wall thickness is 1.47-1.55 meters. The walls of rooms 1 and 3 have checkerboard patterns.

⁴ Бердимуродов А.Э., Сандибоев А.Н., Мураками Т., Бегматов А., Асланов А.П., Алимов Н.Ф. 2023 йилда Кулдортепа ёдгорлигида олиб борилган археологик тадқиқотлар, O'zbekistonda arxeologik tadqiqotlar, Samarqand, 2024. 101-104 b.

⁵ Ахун-бабаев Х.Г. Дворец ишхидов Согда на Афрасиабе.-Самарканд, 1999.-С. 26-27.

As a result of stratigraphic studies carried out in the rooms, floors belonging to three construction periods were identified.

While these rooms were used for defensive purposes during the first construction period, the fragments of household utensils inside the rooms also confirm that they were used for storing products during the second construction period. By the third construction period, the rooms were filled with soil⁶.

In recent years, joint archaeological excavations by Uzbek, Italian and Japanese scientists have been carried out in the arched part of the monument. As a result of the excavations, oval towers located on the four sides of the arch, the inner courtyard of the arch, a terraced platform, the ruler's palace, a residential building, and utility rooms were discovered and studied, which belong to three construction periods.

From the 7th century to the first half of the 8th century - the III construction period.

The middle and end of the 8th century - the II construction period.

The beginning and end of the 9th century - the I construction period.

The monument arch has an open courtyard, a ruler's palace, a utility room, an entrance to the courtyard and towers dating back to the third construction period. There are rooms on three sides of the open courtyard, only the doors of the rooms on the north side lead to the open courtyard through an ayvan. The location of the external entrance to the open courtyard is noted on the south side. The two side walls of this door are made of pakhsa blocks and the top is covered with raw bricks in an arched manner. Initially, the width of the door was 2.8 m., but during the subsequent construction period, the door was narrowed and repaired using raw bricks and its width was 1.6 m. Room No. 15, where the ruler's throne is located, is completely open. This room is rectangular in shape, measuring 6.35x4.75 meters from west to east.

The entrance to the room is located on the south side, its width is 2.1 meters. The floor of the room is covered with baked bricks (46-47x25-26x3.5-4 cm). During the excavations, a room with a ruler's throne was also discovered, and a wooden panel, one of the unique examples of Sogdian art, was found inside the room. Its size is 144-124 centimeters. The panel itself consists of two wide boards, fastened together with iron brackets. On the right side of the board is a composition with carved images of 46 people arranged in four layers⁷.

⁶ Бердимуратов А.Э., Самибоев М. Научный отчёт Сагдийского и Ургутского археологического отряда за 1994 год. Ф.4 Д.239.-Самарканд, 1995.-С. 4-15

⁷ Бердимуратов А.Э., Богомолов Г., Такао Уно. Кофиркальа тилга кирмоқда. Фан ва турмуш. №1-3.-Ташкент, 2018.-Б. 5-7.

In 2007-2008, archaeological excavations were carried out on the right side of the Ilonsay stream, where the Kafirkala pottery jars are located. As a result, a total of 6 pottery jars were discovered and studied. As a result of archaeological research conducted in the Kafirkala arch and pottery jars, samples of vessels such as jars, dates, jugs, pots, bowls, saucers, and oil jars were discovered, which are widespread in the early medieval layers of the monuments of Sughd, Tokharistan, and Fergana. The vessels found in the jars depict a mountain goat and a bull. Researchers emphasize that such images, which are found among handicrafts, are associated with the cult of fertility. About 900 bullae found as a result of archaeological research at the monument serve as the main source for illuminating the political, economic, and cultural history of this oasis, as well as its relations with distant and close peoples. Bullae are a unique archaeological find, usually found on monuments associated with a ruler or a high official. Rulers used bullae to seal and send embassy correspondence, letters and contracts, or important documents. In recent years, based on the evidence of material cultures obtained as a result of archaeological research at the Kofirkala monument, A. Berdimuhamedov puts forward the idea that the center of Rivdat was Kofirkala⁸.

In 2022, a joint Uzbek-Japanese expedition worked together at the Kafirkala monument.

This expedition carried out its work in 3 stages. In the first stage, the floor, which was plastered with thinly sifted greenish-yellow clay, was cleaned. Another horizontal and relatively flat layer was revealed 18–20 cm below it, which rises slightly towards the southern wall and decreases towards the center of the excavation. Below it, a layer mixed with fragments of raw bricks made of greenish-brown clay was discovered. In the second stage, the cleaning of the floor and floors of room 1 along the southern wall continued. The floor was built according to the Sogdian tradition: raw bricks (picked by biting) were stacked three to four rows high along the base of the wall, and the remaining space was filled with soil and compacted. In the third stage, five pits, two tandoors, several ash pits and burnt spots from the hearth, and one semi-underground dwelling were discovered. The semi-underground (poluzemlyanka) was rectangular in shape and extended in a southwest-northeast direction. Its overall dimensions were determined to be 4.2 x 2.6 (1.25) m.

The remains of the city of Dobusiya, one of the largest medieval cities of the Zarafshan oasis, have survived in the form of the Dobuskala monument, which includes the complex of hills of the same name.

⁸ Бердимуродов А.Э., Индиаминова Ш.Э. Буюк Ипак йўли.-Ташкент, 2017.-Б. 96-97

Dobuskala is located in the Pakhtachi district of the Samarkand region, 4 km from the Samarkand-Bukhara highway, in the northeastern part of the village of Dobuskala, on the left bank of the Zarafshan River.

The city is divided into three parts, the main core of the city is the ark.

The ark is located in the northern part of the city, its layout is close to a square, and the ark is separated from the main part of the city by a deep moat.

The city limits completely surround the arch from the north, east and south and have a layout close to a square. The total area of the city limits is 23 ha, and it is protected by massive defensive walls. Research conducted on the defensive walls revealed that there was a wide corridor inside the walls. The Zarafshan River flows through the northern part of the city limits, and this river has now washed away a significant part of it. In the southeast and south of the city limits, a wide defensive ditch 50-60 m wide passes, which separates the city limits from the rabad. The rabad extends south from the city limits. The total area of the rabad is 50 hectares. The entire territory of the rabad is currently covered with a modern cemetery. In recent years, archaeologists Pugachenkova G. A., Rtveladze E. V., Turgunov B. A., Buryakov Yu. F., Rostovsev O. M., Adilov Sh. T. conducted scientific research here, but no major research work was carried out specifically to study the monument. It was during this period that archaeological reconnaissance work was carried out in Dobuskal, and the monument was included in the "Complex of Archaeological Monuments of Uzbekistan".

Archaeological research of Dobusqala began mainly in 2006, by the joint Uzbek-Japanese international expedition of the Institute of Archaeology of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Archaeological excavations were carried out in the Arki, Shahrستان and Rabodi areas of the monument. Over the years, cultural layers of the IV-VI; IX-XII; XV-XVIII centuries were studied in Dobusqala. Among the ceramic objects found and studied in the Arki section, some of them are dated to the VI-IV centuries BC⁹.

Remains of a gate that was in use during the medieval period have been uncovered in the northeastern section of the "shahrستان" (inner city). This gate provided access to a ford across the Zarafshan River, which flowed near the city. Although the city of Dobusiya is mentioned in all medieval historical and geographical texts, the information provided in them is very brief. According to the Arab geographer al-Yaqubi

⁹ Уно Такао, А. Бердимуродов, Г. Богомолов, К. Рахимов ва бошқалар. Кала-и-Дабусия «Согдийский город на Великом Шелковом Пути. // Научные исследования городского центра Средней Азии» Издательство. "Синёса". Киото, Япония 2013.-С.57-59

(d. 905), Sogd was comprised of Samarkand, Dobusiya, Kushaniya, Kesh, and Nasaf." The "History of Bukhara" notes that "Poykent was the name of the village where the king himself resided, while Qal'ayi Dobus was considered the city". Consequently, the city fell to the Arab conquest at a very early stage; the Arabs subsequently refortified it and utilized it as a key military stronghold. At the same time, numerous fortresses surrounding the city were also refortified. Examples of such sites include Qasr al-Bakhili; Qasr ar-Rih (meaning "Castle of the Wind"), located two "farsakhs" from Dobusiya; and Kamarja Fortress, situated east of Dobusiya on the road from Sogd to Arbinjon.

Initial archaeological investigations of the pottery kilns located in the southeastern part of the Dabusia "rabod" (outer city) were conducted in 2007. Excavations continued in 2023 in the area where pottery kilns were located. As a result, the remains of nine single- and double-chambered kilns dating back to the 11th–12th centuries were uncovered and studied¹⁰.

Ceramic slag, melted glass, clay pots, fragments of baked bricks, etc., found during archaeological research in the city, indicate that such crafts as pottery, glassmaking, and blacksmithing were developed in the city. The research yielded a variety of archaeological materials indicating that pottery was developed in the city in the early Middle Ages. The living and utility rooms found on the site of the early medieval palace, which is located in the arch, and the archaeological finds obtained during the study of the outer wall of the palace provide important information about the architecture of the city before the Arab conquest and its specific features. These sources show that Dobusia functioned for two millennia, from early antiquity to the late Middle Ages, first as a fortress on the banks of the Zarafshan River, then as a city, and in later centuries as a village¹¹.

In conclusion, the cities of Central Sogd were one of the major trade and cultural centers not only of the Transoxiana region, but also of all of Central Asia, for more than two millennia. Analysis of written and archaeological materials has also shown that the largest trade turnover on the Great Silk Road fell on the territory of Sogd.

The list of used literatures

1. Асқаров А.А. Ўзбек халқининг келиб чиқиш тарихи.-Тошкент, 2015.-Б. 284, 286.

¹⁰ Бердимуродов А.Э., Сандибоев А.Н., Махамадиев Ғ.И. 2023 йилда Дабусия ёдгорлигида олиб борилган археологик тадқиқотлар. О'zbekistonda arxeologik tadqiqotlar, Samarqand, 2024. 105-109 б.

¹¹ Асланов А.П. Добусия кўхна шаҳри тарихига доир //ЎЗМУ хабарлари.№1\2.2017.–Б.20

2. Асланов А.П. Добусия кўхна шаҳри тарихига доир //ЎзМУ хабарлари.№1\2.2017.–Б.20
3. Ахун-бабаев Х.Г. Дворец ишхидов Согда на Афрасиабе.-Самарканд, 1999.-С. 26-27.
4. Бартольд В.В. Туркестан в эпоху монгольского нашествия , Соч. 9 т. М.: Наука, 1963. Ташкент, I. С. 144 5. С. 186
5. Беленицкий А.М., Бентович О.И., Большаков О.Г. Средневековый город Средней Азии. //Л., 1972,.
6. Бердимуратов А.Э., Матбабаев Б.Х., Мантеллини С., Ронделли Б. Археологические раскопки на городище Кафыр-кала // Археологические исследования в Узбекистане 2004-2005 г. Вып. 5, Ташкент, 2006.-С. 75-76.
7. Бердимуратов А.Э., Ронделли Б. Материалы к археологической карте левобережья Зарафшана // ИМКУ, вып. 35.-Самарканд, 2006.-С. 140. 8.
8. Бердимуратов А.Э., Самибоев М. Научный отчет Сагдийского и Ургутского археологического отряда за 1994 год. Ф.4 Д.239.-Самарканд, 1995.-С. 4-15 9.
9. Бердимуратов А.Э., Богомоллов Г., Такао Уно. Кофиркалга тилга кирмоқда. Фан ва турмуш. №1-3.-Ташкент, 2018.-Б. 5-7. 10.
10. Бердимуратов А.Э., Индиаминова Ш.Э. Буюк Ипак йўли.-Ташкент, 2017.-Б. 96-97
11. Бердимуратов А.Э., Мантеллини С., Матбабаев Б. Х. (Узбекистан, Италия). Кафиркала загородная резиденция Самаркандских правителей // Самарканднинг умумбашарий мадания тараккиёт тарихида тутган ўрни.-Тошкент-Самарканд, 2007.
12. Бердимуратов А.Э., Сандибоев А.Н., Махаммадиев Ф.И. 2023 йилда Дабусия ёдгорлигида олиб борилган археологик тадқиқотлар. O‘zbekistonda arxeologik tadqiqotlar, Samarqand, 2024. 105 109 б.
13. Бердимуратов А.Э., Сандибоев А.Н., Мураками Т., Бегматов А., Асланов А.П., Алимов Н.Ф. 2023 йилда Кулдортепа ёдгорлигида олиб борилган археологик тадқиқотлар, O‘zbekistonda arxeologik tadqiqotlar, Samarqand, 2024. 101-104 б. 14.
14. Бердимуратов А.Э., Токао Уно, Рахимов К.А. Добусияда ўтказилган археологик тадқиқотлар ҳақида. // Археологические исследования в Узбекистане 2006-2007 года. Выпуск-6, Ташкент, 2009.-С. 76-95
15. Гойипов Б. Суғд конфедерацияси шакилланиши, тараккиёти ва таназзули.-Тошкент, 2015.-Б. 129.

16. Сандибоев А.Н., Мураками Т., Бегматов А., Махамадиев Ғ. 2023 йилда Қўрғонтепа ёдгорлигида олиб борилган археологик тадқиқотлар, O‘zbekistonda arxeologik tadqiqotlar, Samarqand, 2024.389-391 b.
17. УноТакао, А. Бердимуродов, Г. Богомоллов, К. Рахимов ва бошқалар. Кала-и-Дабусия «Согдийский город на Великом Шелковом Пути. // Научные исследования городского центра Средней Азии» Издательство. “Синёся”. Киото, Япония2013.-С.57-59